

A new flavonol glycoside from the root of *Sida rhombifolia*

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Abstract : A new flavonol glycoside **1**, m.p. 173–175 °C, mol. formula : C₂₃H₂₄O₁₂, [M⁺] 492 (FABMS) has been isolated from ethanolic extract of *Sida rhombifolia*. Compound **1** has been characterized as 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavonol-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside by chemical, spectral and elemental analysis.

Keywords : *Sida rhombifolia*, Malvaceae, flavonol glycoside.

Introduction

Sida rhombifolia Linn. belong to family Malvaceae. It is commonly known as “Mahabala” in Ayurveda. It is a weed of marshy places through India¹. The root and leaves are aphrodisiac, tonic, useful in fever, heart diseases, burning sensation, piles and all kinds of inflammation. Munda tribes apply pounded leaves on swelling². Total alcoholic extract of the root of *Sida rhombifolia* Linn. has shown significant anti-inflammatory, antipyretic³, and antibacterial activity³ anti-noceptive and anti-inflammatory activity of *Sida rhombifolia* leaves⁴, hepatoprotective⁵ lipid lowering, anti-oxidant⁶. From the aerial part *n*-alkane long chain alcohols, sterols⁷, ephedrine, sterculic acid, linoleic acid C-phenylethylamine, cellulose, lignin⁸. Literature survey reveals that no work on structural elucidation was carried out on the roots of *S. rhombifolia*. In the present work we report the isolation and structural elucidation of new flavonol glycoside **1** (5,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavonol-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside).

Results and discussion

The ethanolic extract of the root of this plant afforded a novel flavonol glycoside **1**, mol. formula : C₂₃H₂₄O₁₂, m.p. 173–175 °C, and *m/z* : 492 [M⁺], 330 [M-sugar], 274, 168, 134. It gave molisch and sinoda test⁹ showing its flavonol glycoside nature. IR spectra showed absorp-

tion band at 3445 (-OH), 1658 and 1549 cm⁻¹ for an α,β-unsaturated ketone (C₄ of flavonol), 2880 (-OMe), 845 and 639 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of *p*-disubstituted benzene. The band in its UV spectrum at 360 and 268 nm showed its flavonoid skeleton. The bathochromic shift of 55 nm with NaOMe indicating the presence of hydroxyl group¹⁰ at C-4'. The bathochromic shift in both band (Band I and II) in presence of AlCl₃ indicated the presence of two hydroxy group at position C-3 and C-5. The hydroxy group at C-5 was further confirmed by 45 nm. Bathochromic shift of band II with the addition of AlCl₃-HCl. No shift with CH₃COONa/MeOH in band II showing the absence of hydroxyl group¹¹ at C-7.

In ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **1** exhibit one proton singlet at δ 6.62 (1H, s, H-8) and two doublet signal at δ 8.02 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2', H-6') and δ 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3', H-5') suggested the typical A₂B₂ splitting pattern of ring B. This clearly shows that one proton is present in ring A, thus the position of protons¹² are at C-8, C-2', C-3', C-5' and C-6'. The anomeric proton signal at δ 5.5 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz) and a broad signal at δ 3.2–3.8 corresponding to seven sugars proton showing the presence of one glucose moiety. The coupling constant of 7.1 Hz for the anomeric proton of glucose confirmed the β-configuration of D-glucose. Two singlet signal at δ 3.42 and 3.2 ppm each corresponding to three

proton shows the presence of two methoxy group at C-6 and C-7 position. The signal at δ 60.15 and 60.03 ppm in ^{13}C NMR spectra, further confirm the presence of -OMe group at C-6 and C-7 position. The characteristic ion appeared at m/z : 492 [M^+], 330 [M-sugar], 274, 168, 134.

Acid hydrolysis of compound **1** with 7% ethanolic H_2SO_4 gave aglycone **2**, m.p. 170 °C, mol. formula : $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7$, m/z : 330 [M^+] which was identity as 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavonol by comparison of its elemental and spectral analysis data (UV, IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) with literature value. The aqueous hydrolysate, after the removal of aglycone, was neutralize with BaCO_3 and BaSO_4 and filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subject to paper chromatography using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent. Sugar was identified as D-glucose (R_f 0.19 by co-paper chromatography). Periodate oxidation of compound **1**, confirmed that the sugar were present in pyranose form. The relative location of the sugar moiety in compound **1** were determined by permethylation followed by acid hydrolysis which yielded methylated sugars and methylated aglycone. The methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose (by co-paper chromatography). The methylated aglycone, mol. formula : $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$, m.p. 155–160 °C, m/z : 358 [M^+], identified as 5,6,7,4'-tetramethoxyflavonol, since C-3 hydroxy group of the flavonol was non-methylated hence it was concluded that sugar must be linked at C-3 of the aglycone. The attachment of sugar-linkage at C-3 of the aglycone was further confirmed by comparing the ^{13}C NMR spectra of glycoside with the aglycone. The C-3 of the glycoside in ^{13}C NMR spectra appeared at high field (130.8 ppm) than C-3 of the agly-

cone (135.2 ppm). Thus C-3 of the glycoside showed shielding effect, confirmed the attachment of sugar at C-3 of the aglycone through C-O-C linkage.

When compound **1** was hydrolysed with enzyme emulsin (β -glucosidase) it liberates free sugar. Since emulsin is a specific enzyme for the hydrolysis of β -linkage so it was conclude that linkage between sugar moiety and hydroxy group of aglycone was β - in nature on the basis of above finding. The structure of compound **1** was characterize as 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavonol-3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside.

Experimental

General experimental procedure :

All the melting points were determined by open glass capillary method and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer. UV spectra were recorded on Beckmans-DK2 spectrophotometers. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded at 300 MHz and ^{13}C NMR spectra at 100 MHz in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal reference on a JEOL JNM-A 500 spectrometer and mass spectra on JEOL Sx-102 (FAB) mass spectrometer.

Plant material :

The root of *Sida rhombifolia* were collected from NRIPT (Northern Regional Institute of Printing Technology) ground, Teliarganj, Allahabad and the plants were identify by Dr. B. K. Shukla, Botanist, Botanical Survey of India (BSI), Allahabad.

Extraction and isolation :

Air dried powdered root (4 kg) was extracted with 95% ethanol in a soxhlet apparatus for 10 h. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure by rotatory evaporator and concentrated ethanolic extract was poured into separating funnel and mix with solvent in increasing polarity, shake well and separated into aqueous and organic layer. On this basis different fraction were obtained like hexane, benzene, chloroform, butanol, ethyl acetate and methanol fraction. The ethyl acetate soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield brown viscous mass. It shows one spot on TLC examination using solvent system CHCl_3 :

MeOH (8 : 2, v/v). The compound were separated by column chromatography over silica gel and purified by preparative TLC.

Study of compound 1 :

Compound 1 was recrystallized from methanol as light yellow needles. Mol. formula : $C_{23}H_{24}O_{12}$, m.p. 173–175 °C, m/z : 492 [M^+], 330 [M-sugar], 274, 168, 134; found (%) : C, 54.45, H, 5.25; Calcd. (%) : C, 54.35, H, 5.33; UV (MeOH) λ_{max} (nm) : 360, 268; (CH₃OH/AlCl₃) 380, 278, 400sh, 288sh; (CH₃OH/AlCl₃/HCl) 405, 268, 313sh; (CH₃OH/fused/NaOAc) 360, 283; (MeOH/NaOMe) 415, 268, 470; IR γ_{max} (KBr) : 3450 (-OH), 2940 (-CH aromatic), 2880 (-OMe), 1690 (>C=O), 1650 (aromatic ring system), 1185 (C-O-C), 845, 639 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.42 (3H, s, -OMe-6), 3.32 (3H, s, OMe-7), 6.85 (1H, s, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 8.02 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 5.50 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz, anomeric), 3.20–3.86 (7H, m, sugar proton); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 154.3 (C-2, s), 130.8 (C-3, s), 176.8 (C-4, s), 158.2 (C-5, s), 132.0 (C-6, s), 155.1 (C-7, s), 127.8 (C-8, d), 149.6 (C-9, s), 104.2 (C-10, s), 121.6 (C-1', s), 112.1 (C-2', d), 148 (C-3', d), 149.2 (C-4', d), 115.9 (C-5', d), 122.2 (C-6', d), 60.15 (-OCH₃, q), 60.03 (-OCH₃, q), 98.3 (C''-1, d), 76.5 (C''-2, d), 74.6 (C''-3, d), 67.3 (C''-4, d), 74.7 (C''-5, d), 60.5 (C''-6, t).

Acid hydrolysis of compound 1 :

150 mg of compound 1 was dissolve in ethanol (25 mL) and refluxed with 15 mL of 7% H₂SO₄ on water bath for 8 h. The content were concentrated and allowed to cool and residue was extracted with diethyl ether. The ether layer was washed with water and the residue was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using CHCl₃ : MeOH (8 : 2, v/v) to give compound 2, which was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavonol by comparison with its known spectral referred data. The aqueous hydrolysate was neutralize with BaCO₃ and BaSO₄ and filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subject to paper chromatography examination using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent, sugar were identified as D-glucose (*R_f* 0.19).

Study of compound 2 :

Mol. formula : $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$, m.p. 170 °C; Found (%) : C, 58.7; H, 3.33. Calcd. (%) : C, 60.0; H, 2.8; IR γ_{max} (KBr) : 3450, 2940, 2880, 1690, 1650, 1185, 845, 639 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.32 (3H, s, OCH₃-7), 3.42 (3H, s, OCH₃-6), 5.35 (2H, s, Ar-OH-5,4'), 6.18–7.59 (5H, m, ArH), 16.77 (1H, s, C₃-OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 154.3 (C-2, s), 130.8 (C-3, s), 176.8 (C-4, s), 158.2 (C-5, s), 132.0 (C-6, s), 155.1 (C-7, s), 127.8 (C-8, d), 149.6 (C-9, s), 104.2 (C-10, s), 121.6 (C-1', s), 112.1 (C-2', d), 148 (C-3', d), 149.2 (C-4', d), 115.9 (C-5', d), 122.2 (C-6', d), 60.15 (-OCH₃, q), 60.03 (-OCH₃, q); Mass m/z : 330 [M^+], 302, 274, 168, 138.

Permethylation of compound 1 :

Compound 1 (150 mg) was refluxed with MeI (5 ml) and Ag₂O (35 ml) in DMF (5.0 mg) for one day and then filtered. The filtrate was hydrolyzed with 7% ethanolic H₂SO₄ for 8 h to give the methylated aglycone 3, identified as 5,6,7,4'-tetramethoxyflavonol and methylated sugars which were identified as 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose.

Study of compound 3 :

Mol. formula : $C_{19}H_{15}O_7$, m.p. 162–165 °C; [M^+] 355 (FABMS); Found (%) : C, 60.50; H 5.85. Calcd. (%) :

C, 60.48; H, 4.87; IR γ_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3450, 3013, 2940, 2864, 1650, 1621, 1497, 832; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 3.89 (3H, s, -OMe-5), 6.85 (1H, s, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 3.42 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.32 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 8.02 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz H-2', H-6'), 7.12 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3', H-5').

Enzymatic hydrolysis of compound 1 :

Compound 1 (20 mg) was dissolved in MeOH (25 ml) and hydrolysed with equal volume of almond emulsin. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for two days and filtered. Residue are identify as 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavonol.

The hydrolysate was concentrated and subject to paper chromatography examination using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) as solvent, which shows the presence of D-glucose (R_f 0.19).

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References

1. Anonymous, "Dictionary of Indian Medicinal Plants", CIMAP, Lucknow, India, 1992, 421.
2. K. R. Kirthikar and B. D. Basu, *An Indian Medicinal Plants*, 1981, **1**, 310.
3. M. Alam, S. Joy and U. Ali, *Indian Drugs*, 1991, **28**, 397.
4. S. Venkatesh, Y. S. Reddy, B. Suresh, B. M. Reddy and M. Ramesh, *J. Ethnopharmacology*, 1999, **67**, 229.
5. K. S. Rao and S. H. Mishra, *Indian J. Pharmacology*, 1997, **29**, 110.
6. Thounaojam, D. K. Patel, R. Singh, V. Devkar and A. V. Ramchandran, *J. Experimental and Toxicologic Pathology*, 2010, **1**, 111.
7. M. M. Goyal and K. K. Rani, *Fitoterapia*, 1989, **60**, 163.
8. A. Chatterjee and S. Chandraprakash, "The Treatise on Indian Medicinal Plants", Publications and Information Directorate, New Delhi, 1992, **2**, 185.
9. J. B. Harborne, T. J. Mabry and H. Mabry, "The Flavonoides", Chapman and Hall, London, 1975, 65.
10. T. J. Marby, K. R. Markham and M. B. Thomas, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoid", Springer, Heidelberg, 1970, 35.
11. J. A. Neberto, J. Adell, O. Barbera and D. Strack, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 1513.
12. K. V. Rao, A. G. Damu, B. Jayaprakasham and D. Gunasekar, *J. Natural Product*, 1999, **62**, 30.